

Dialogue tool

How to value science communication activities in academic and research careers at the EU and national levels

A roadmap of solutions

ENJOI

ENJOI - Engagement and JOURNALISM Innovation for Outstanding Open Science Communication
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This dialogue tool aims to facilitate the discussion about how to value science communication in research and academic careers by focusing on the solutions and the road ahead

How to value science communication activities as an important part of the academic/research career path at the EU and national levels?

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Credits

Original idea: Participants of the ENJOI EW in Brussels (March/2022) and NEWSERA workshops in Portugal (Nov/2022)

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The ENJOI logo, where the letter 'J' is stylized as a pencil tip pointing upwards.